

Comparative Evaluation of Teaching Aptitude among Teacher Education Trainees in Haryana

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Abstract : Teaching aptitude is a condition or set of characteristics that estimates the extent to which the individual will profit from the specified course of training, or forecast the quality of his/her achievement in a new situation. Teacher education and teaching aptitudes are intricately related to students' learning outcomes. Today's students become tomorrow's teachers. Today's teachings develop teaching aptitudes, and generate learning outcomes. The main objective of the study to compare the teaching aptitude of male and female pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana. The sample of the study consisted of 200 elementary teacher trainees (100 male and 100 female) studying in government and private elementary teacher trainees of Eastern Haryana. The Result of the Study : There exists no significant difference in Teaching Aptitude Scores of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana and no significant difference in Teaching Aptitude Scores of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana.

India has made progress in many aspects which is being acknowledged worldwide. Today, India's economy is among the fastest growing economies of the world even when the developed world is faced with severe recession, leading to unprecedented unemployment. India's IT industry boom and its technical knowhow in this area have placed India in a unique position in the world. Its citizens are being viewed with respect and admiration. However it's progress on basic education leaves a lot to be desired. India is also a country of young people. More than 50% of its population being young, places India in a very advantageous position. It can clearly avail of the demographic dividend. But this demographic dividend may turn into liability unless education and skill levels of its youth are significantly improved. One of the key challenges is to have growth with equity and democracy without which the current growth becomes unsustainable. Ensuring good quality education for its population particularly up to completion of secondary school is an indispensable step in the direction of bringing equity and enhancing democracy.

Government school system in India caters to children living in villages and small towns, which is a fairly large proportion of the Indian population. It consists of 77 percent of our country's total population of 860 million. The extremely poor quality of education available to them ensures that a large majority of India's children continue to be far behind. One of the main reasons, for such a dismal state of our public system of schools is that the local communities have not been able to assert themselves and effect desirable changes. It is ironical that education can be a great leveller and also be a means to perpetuate the existing social divide. Great hierarchy in schooling provisions exist in India. Equality of opportunity in terms of accessing school, have remained at best a political rhetoric. India's middle class who can afford to pay for their children's education opt for sending their children to high fee paying private schools and for rest of the masses poorly equipped barely functioning government schools remain the sole option. The social and economic divide that exists in society is reflected in access to schools as well. The government run school system is heterogeneous and has large variety within it. On the one hand, we have single teacher, building less multi-grade EGS schools and on the other, a class of comfortably funded - Central Schools and Navodaya Vidyalayas which target a limited set of children (of government employees). Amongst these lie majority of India's schools which continue to be managed and funded by the government and dot the rural landscape of India. A study conducted by Miguel and Barsaga (1997, p.120) considered factors affecting pupil performance, investigated the variables of teacher, student, parents and community, and concluded that the teacher quality was the key factor. Chau, (1996) found that particularly in the initial stages of education, and especially in the rural areas, the quality of education depends on the quality of teachers. With National Curriculum Framework on Teacher Education (NCFTE), as a part of Right to Education (RTE) Act coming into effect in 2009, there has been an increasing recognition of the importance of teacher education, on the stream of thought that: only quality teaching can provide quality education. The 12th five year plan too recognizes that "Teachers and Teaching are central to School Quality."

While there is emphasis for teacher education schemes and frameworks on quality teacher training for transforming primary education, the approach is unidirectional i.e. from teachers to the students. There is hardly any stress on the *two-way* causal relationship between learning outcomes and the quality of teachers. The underlying assumption by the policymakers is that quality teaching is a result of two years of quality training only and previously completed twelve years of schooling has no role to play in shaping of student teachers. Such assumption may result from the social hierarchy that rigidly distinguishes between the teacher and the student, making the policy-makers unable to recognize the fact that the future teachers are

essentially the students from the same government schools which have poor learning outcomes.

The teacher education institutes are not magical factories that'll produce the living encyclopaedias' in merely two years!. It is in 2012, that the guidelines on restructuring and revitalizing DIETs in the 12th Plan draft mentions about the interdependence between continuous teacher professional development and school improvement, but only to base its focus on the former. It is least realized that teachers are being made since the day they are born, not just when they enroll in a two year diploma in education course. It is yesterday's students who become today's teachers and today's students that will become tomorrow's teachers. The teachers are essentially students, and students are prospective teachers: the roles are interchangeable and complementary.

The concentrated view of teacher training is also reflected in another problem: teacher quality seems to be most frequently measured in terms of academic credentials. Academic achievement links the twelve years of schooling with the two years of pre-service training in elementary education. The basis for admission in Diploma in Education in government-run District Institutes of Education and Training in Haryana is percentage in boards³, which is a terminal evaluation of the specified syllabus, with no measurement of teaching aptitude that would capture the multiplicity of experiences of everyday life that forms characteristics symptomatic of performance as teachers. There is little or no evidence that higher credentials or pre-service training lead to better quality of teaching. In fact, studies show that even achievement in degree exams don't correlate with teaching aptitudes, let alone high school exams! Schiefelbein & Simmons (1981) reviewed research in more than 20 countries, and found that teachers without certificates in educational training had students who performed as well as those with certificates in 19 out of 32 studies. They concluded, "Teacher certification should be reviewed with caution as a way to increase student achievement". They also found that years of teacher experience was a significant determinant of student achievement in only 7 out of 19 studies, and that more years of teacher training was not related to higher student achievement in 5 out of 6 studies. Further, Sajan, 2000 found that the level of achievement in degree exam has no influence in predicting teaching aptitude. Due to subtle differences between the various psychological constructs, a cobweb of misconceptions has developed about the construct "aptitude". Often it is used as a synonym of intelligence, personality, capability and innate ability. But according to the Warren's Dictionary of Psychology, aptitude is a "a condition or set of characteristics regarded as symptomatic of an individual's ability to acquire to acquire training in some (usually specified) knowledge, skill, or set of responses such as the ability to speak a language, to produce music etc."The definition clarifies that: It is "the ability" to acquire, reflecting

cumulative influence of the array of experience in everyday life. Essentially, aptitude is the result of both heredity and environment. It embraces any characteristic that predisposes to learning, which might include personality, intelligence, and knowledge. But the point is it is not solely reducible to any one of these. Simply defined, it is the potential to acquire or perform in a new situation. Teaching aptitude is a condition or set of characteristics that estimates the extent to which the individual will profit from the specified course of training, or forecast the quality of his/her achievement in a new situation. According to the instrument that the study employs, the Teaching Aptitude Test Battery by Singh and Sharma, teaching aptitude includes the following five areas: a) Mental ability b) Professional information c) Adaptability d) Attitude towards children e) Interest in Profession. Teacher education and teaching aptitudes are intricately related to students' learning outcomes. Today's students become tomorrow's teachers. Today's teachings develop teaching aptitudes, and generate learning outcomes. Teachers' education adds to the teacher-making process. Teachers teach, and produce learning outcomes. As defined previously in the paper, teaching aptitude is a broad term, encompassing any characteristic that predisposes to learn. The student outcomes in relevant areas as well as teacher education therefore itself predisposes to the formation of teacher aptitude. With the poor status of the teacher training institutes, the quality of future teachers is under scanner. A study of the teaching aptitudes, especially of the II year students will indeed give us an output-oriented status report of DIETs.

- Objectives :-**
1. To compare the teaching aptitude of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana.
 2. To compare the teaching aptitude of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana.

Hypotheses of the Study

Following Hypotheses were constructed to achieve the objective of the study:

1. There exists no significant difference in teaching aptitude of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana.
2. There exists no significant difference in the teaching aptitude of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana.

Design of the Study

Population

The population of the study comprised all the elementary teacher trainees of Eastern Haryana.

Sample

Sample of the present study consisted of 200 elementary teacher trainees (100 male and 100 female) studying in government and private elementary teacher trainees of Eastern Haryana.

Tools used

In order to attain the objectives of the study, tool to measure the teaching aptitude was needed. For this investigator used Teaching Aptitude Test Battery (T A T B) by Shamim Karim & Ashok Kumar. This test aims to measure the aptitude in teaching profession. There are 80 items related to 8 areas or sub-test. Each sub-test contains 10 items. The 8 sub tests are related to the eight areas of teaching aptitude.

Data analysis and results:

The first main objective of the study was to compare the teaching aptitude of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana. In order to find out whether there exists any significant difference in the Teaching aptitude pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana. t-test was computed and the results thus obtained is shown in the table 1.

Table 1: Showing Comparison of Teaching Aptitude Scores of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana (N = 200)

Measure	Training institution	Mean	SD	t-value
Teaching Aptitude	Government	219.96	18.86	1.45
	Private	217.26	18.42	

Observation of the table shows that the Teaching Aptitude Scores of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana is 1.45 which is less than the required value (2.63) for significance at .01 levels. This indicates that there exists no significant difference in Teaching Aptitude Scores of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana. Same is depicted in the graph 1.

The second objective of study was to compare the teaching aptitude of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana. In order to find out whether there exists any significant difference in the Teaching aptitude of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana. t-test was computed and the results thus obtained is shown in the table 2.

Table 2: Showing Comparison of Teaching Aptitude Scores of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana (N = 200)

Measure	Gender	Mean	SD	t-value
Teaching Aptitude	Male	216.18	15.05	2.13
	Female	219.05	21.47	

Observation of the table shows that the Teaching Aptitude Scores of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana is 2.13 which is less than the required value (2.63) for significance at .01 levels. This indicates that there exists is no significant difference in Teaching Aptitude Scores of pre-service male and female teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana. Same is depicted in the graph 2.

Results:

1. There exists no significant difference in Teaching Aptitude Scores of pre-service teachers of government and private Elementary Teacher Training Institutes of Haryana
2. No significant difference in Teaching Aptitude Scores of male and female pre-service teachers of Elementary Teacher Training Institute of Haryana.

References

1. Adval, S.B. (1952). *An introduction into qualities of teachers under training*. Unpublished doctoral thesis. Edu. University of Baroda.
2. Anwar, M. N., Naz, A., Haq, R., & Bibi, C. (2012). *An Examination of Teaching Aptitude of Teachers Working at Primary Level: Demographic differences*. *International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education*, 1(2).
3. Beena, S (1995). *Determinants of Teacher effectiveness*. Ambala Cantt: The Indian Publications.
4. Beet, EA (1973). Astronomy in School. (EJ 088504). *Physics Education*, 8, 7, 437-442.
5. Botterbusch , K. F. (1978). *Psychological Testing in Vocational Evaluation in Psychological testing*.

6. Kaur, D & Abdullah, S. (2007) A Study on Academic Achievement, Teaching Aptitude and the Personality Traits as the predictors of success in Elementary Teacher Training unpublished doc. Jamiya Miriya Islamiya, New Delhi.
7. Breen, M.J. (1979). *Teacher Interest and Student Attitude toward Four areas of Elementary School Curriculum*.
8. Buch, MB *Third Survey of Research in Education*. New Delhi: NCERT.